

PEDAGOGICAL POTENTIAL OF ABDULLA AVLONI'S EDUCATIONAL VIEWS IN TEACHING JADID SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE TO FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18466691>

***Abstract.** The article analyzes the pedagogical potential of Abdulla Avloni's educational views in teaching Jadid scientific heritage to future history teachers. It highlights the significance of Avloni's ideas on education and upbringing in organizing the educational process and their impact on the professional and moral development of the younger generation in the context of globalization.*

***Keywords:** pedagogy, education, enlightenment, modernism, new method schools, newspaper, magazine, "Turon" theater troupe.*

INTRODUCTION

"At the moment when our country is entering a new, high stage of its development, we need mature personnel who have been brought up in the spirit of national values along with the achievements of Western science, like our ancestors" [3], President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasizes. Uzbekistan has chosen a gradual and consistent path of development aimed at building a prosperous future and achieving the level of developed countries. In this process, universal human values, along with national traditions, customs, and moral qualities historically inherent in the Uzbek mentality, serve as an important foundation. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev notes: "It is natural that the legacy of our enlightened ancestors serves as a foundation for the legal democratic state and civil society that we are building today. Whether someone likes it or not, our people must follow the path shown by our ancestors, because their ideas and programs are fully harmonious with the strategy of building a New Uzbekistan" [1].

These ideas highlight the relevance of drawing on the intellectual and pedagogical heritage of enlightened thinkers in educating the younger generation. In particular, the issue of moral and professional upbringing of youth occupies a special place in the context of the state program aimed at strengthening dialogue with the people and prioritizing human interests. Abdulla Avloni, an active representative of the Jadid movement that emerged in the early twentieth century, devoted his life to enlightening the nation, educating children, and raising a generation of knowledgeable, socially responsible individuals. His activities were directed toward the formation of educated specialists and the aspiration for a free and prosperous homeland. The Uzbek people possess a rich historical, spiritual, and cultural heritage shaped over centuries. The legacy left by prominent enlightened thinkers continues to serve as a guiding framework for contemporary education. In this regard, the scientific and pedagogical heritage of Abdulla Avloni holds particular significance. His works are distinguished by their strong educational and moral orientation and remain relevant for the preparation of future history teachers in modern educational practice.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In the course of the research, the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the works of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, scholarly literature related to the topic, and relevant

Internet sources were analyzed. The study employed general scientific research methods, including theoretical analysis, deduction, analysis and synthesis, and logical reasoning.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Abdulla Avloni is one of the prominent figures of Uzbek national culture of the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. He was an enlightened poet, playwright, journalist, pedagogue, scholar, and public figure who played a significant role during the period of profound cultural and social change in Turkestan. As an active representative of the Jadid movement, Avloni advanced progressive ideas aimed at national awakening and enlightenment, considering education as the main driving force of social development. Throughout his career, Abdulla Avloni worked as a teacher and pedagogue, laying the foundations of modern Uzbek pedagogy and the methodology of teaching the Uzbek language and literature. His educational ideas are distinguished by their deep moral and spiritual content. The importance he attached to knowledge and enlightenment is clearly reflected in his poetic works. For example, in the following lines, Avloni expresses his devotion to science and learning:

The son of man is perfected through knowledge, Beauty and wealth are insufficient without it. Knowledge is a necessary light, like a burning candle, to know God without knowledge is a meaningless proverb [4]. Through these lines, Avloni emphasizes that knowledge is the main source of human perfection and moral maturity. He compares knowledge to vital necessities, such as food, water, and air, showing that intellectual and spiritual development is impossible without learning. According to Avloni, ignorance deprives a person of true understanding, while knowledge illuminates both the individual and society. This idea remains relevant today, as lack of education often leads to social and moral problems.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev has also highlighted the contemporary significance of Avloni's legacy, noting that the work *"Turkish Gulistan or Ethics"*, created on the basis of centuries-old national values, has not lost its importance as a unique guide to moral education. The President emphasizes that Avloni's educational and ethical ideas are especially valuable in the modern period, when national spirituality understanding is being restored. In addition, works such as *"The First Teacher," "The Second Teacher,"* and *"Tarihi Anbiyo"* play an important role in the moral and intellectual education of the younger generation.

Abdulla Avloni (1878–1934) devoted his life to spreading progressive ideas through education. In 1904, he opened a new-method (Jadid) school in the Mirabad district of Tashkent, where secular subjects such as native language, literature, geography, history, arithmetic, and natural sciences were taught alongside moral education. In 1909, he established the charitable organization *"Jamiyati Hayriya"*, which provided financial support for the education of children from low-income families and orphans [7;8.]. Later, in 1912, he opened a two-grade school in the Degrez district of Tashkent. Avloni authored and published numerous textbooks and manuals for new-method schools, including *"The First Teacher"* (1911), *"The Second Teacher"* (1912), *"Turkish Gulistan or Ethics"* (1913), *"School Gulistan"* (1915), and collections such as *"Literature and National Poems"* (1909–1915).

These works played a crucial role in shaping the content and methodology of national education. From 1921 onward, Abdulla Avloni actively participated in teacher training, women's education, and the development of educational institutions. He held various positions, including head of educational institutions, teacher at the Tashkent Military School, and professor and head of the language and literature department at the Central Asian University. His scientific and

creative heritage includes textbooks, dramas, critical articles, and thousands of poetic lines written under various pseudonyms.

Historically, education in Turkestan during the nineteenth century was largely limited to religious instruction in mosques and madrasas. With the emergence of colonial educational policies, secular knowledge was introduced, but often in a bureaucratic and ideologically biased manner. In response, Avloni sought to create a national model of education that combined universal human values with national identity. Reflecting on this struggle, he wrote: “When ignorant people learned that I taught about the earth, people, mountains, rivers, and the sky in my school, they accused me of unbelief and closed the school” [6]. Despite such resistance, Abdulla Avloni remained committed to his educational mission and continued promoting enlightenment. His pedagogical heritage demonstrates strong potential for teaching Jadid scientific heritage to future history teachers by integrating moral education, national values, and modern scientific knowledge. Although the Russian authorities attempted to suppress modern schools, Avloni later opened a two-grade school in the Degrez district of Tashkent, where geography, history, arithmetic, geometry, natural sciences (physics), as well as native language and literature were taught [9]. His textbooks combined writing instruction with short didactic texts designed to develop reading comprehension and moral education.

MAIN PART

As an active and nationally oriented participant of the Jadid movement, Abdulla Avloni created numerous artistic and journalistic works aimed at improving the literacy of children in the Turkestan region and developing their spiritual and moral worldview. In the *usuli jadid* schools that he established, including those opened in his own home, Avloni prepared and used such educational resources as “*Literature or National Poems*,” “*The First Teacher*,” “*The Second Teacher*,” “*School Gulistan*,” and “*Turkish Gulistan or Morals*.” These textbooks were not limited to teaching basic reading and writing skills. They played an important role in shaping students’ independent thinking, goal-setting abilities, and moral consciousness. Avloni clearly understood the pedagogical value of artistic creativity in developing children’s imaginative and critical thinking. In a period when national identity and spiritual maturity were under ideological pressure, such an approach was especially significant.

Historical experience shows that expressive reading is one of the key objectives of literary education, as it enables learners to comprehend the content and meaning of a literary text more deeply. Through expressive and meaningful reading, the events and ideas of a work come vividly before the reader. Avloni paid equal attention to literacy, reading comprehension, and emotional perception of artistic texts, considering them essential components of effective education. It is well known from pedagogical history that teaching children expressive reading is one of the main tasks of literary education. Expressive reading ensures a deeper understanding of a literary text, allowing the content, images, and events of a work to vividly appear before the reader. Abdulla Avloni attached equal importance to literacy and to reading comprehension, emphasizing the emotional perception and aesthetic appreciation of artistic works as essential components of education [11].

Abdulla Avloni also paid special attention to the education of socially vulnerable children, particularly orphans in need of protection. In 1909, under his leadership, the charitable organization “*Jamiyati Khairiya*” was established to educate orphaned children. Later, he opened a two-grade school in the Degrez district of Tashkent, where secular subjects were taught. Despite resistance from the colonial authorities, Avloni continued his educational activities without abandoning his progressive views. In 1913, he actively participated in the establishment of the

“*Turon*” theater troupe, aiming to protect society from harmful external influences and to strengthen national consciousness. By translating foreign literary works into Uzbek and staging them, he contributed to the spiritual development of society through national theatrical art.

According to Abdulla Avloni, moral education is the most important factor that elevates a person’s dignity and social status. He divided human behavior into good and bad, explaining that disciplined behavior formed through education leads to virtue, while the absence of upbringing results in immoral conduct. He described ethics as a science that explains good and bad behavior through evidence and examples, emphasizing that a morally educated person understands personal responsibility, values knowledge and scholars, and strives for self-improvement. He cited the hadith stating that no deed weighs heavier than good character, as righteous behavior elevates a believer to a high spiritual rank. Avloni further emphasized that a human being consists of two interconnected elements: the body and the soul [10].

While the body perceives the external world, the soul distinguishes good from evil. Moral character, which reflects the state of the soul, cannot be seen with the eye but is measured through behavior. He argued that expecting virtue from a person raised without education and morals is unrealistic, comparing it to seeking fruit from barren land. A rich scientific and pedagogical heritage of spiritual and moral education has been passed down from Abdulla Avloni. In modern pedagogical research, his poems and stories should be studied in higher education institutions as effective tools for students’ spiritual and moral development. This heritage can be systematically applied through the following educational directions:

As folk wisdom states, “*It is better to be a shepherd in one’s own homeland than a sultan in a foreign land*” [10]. This idea of devotion to the homeland is deeply reflected in Abdulla Avloni’s poetic works: I am not guilty, my homeland, my mountains, I left you too early, my dear gardens. Separation torments my soul, My days are filled with sorrow. Avloni’s work “*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*,” which he described as intended for older children, is regarded as a model educational text. The author noted that he wrote this work under the influence of the Persian poet Saadi Shirazi’s “*Gulistan*.” Avloni explained his motivation as follows: “*Encouraged by the requests of several fellow teachers, I found the courage and enthusiasm to write and publish this work. Praise be to God, I succeeded on my second attempt, because schools in Turkestan are in great need of a perfect ethical book written in our own language (Uzbek), including teachers themselves*” [5].

Avloni emphasized that “*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*” was prepared for literature enthusiasts, ethical scholars, and for use in upper grades of the first new-method schools. The emotional depth of his concern for the nation is expressed in the following lines: *Every day until evening I grieve, Every night my inner fire burns. No one knows my pain, Why is my nation ill?* The effectiveness of Avloni’s poems “*Vatan*” and “*The Word of Hijran*” is explained by several factors: these poems were written specifically for students; they correspond to learners’ age, worldview, and intellectual level; their content is conveyed in clear and fluent language; and despite being written nearly a century ago, they remain relevant to modern literary language. Avloni’s patriotic poems and stories glorifying the homeland possess significant social and pedagogical value in studying early twentieth-century educational thought. Their potential in fostering patriotism within the educational system remains highly effective.

A separate chapter of “*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*” entitled “*Munislik*” is devoted to educating students in the spirit of friendship and companionship. In this chapter, *munislik* is defined as finding one’s equal, sharing wealth, and enjoying sincere communication with loyal

friends. Avloni distinguishes between true and false friends, teaching students to recognize sincerity, avoid hypocrisy, and distance themselves from deceitful companionship. In his pedagogical practice, Avloni effectively employed the storytelling method, drawing on Eastern—particularly Uzbek—folk traditions, classical Eastern poetry, and examples from Hadith literature. He frequently used poetic narratives to convey moral lessons. In the chapter “*Munislik*,” the following poem is presented in a narrative form [10]: *A true friend forgives his friend, Words spoken face to face. A false friend has a thousand tongues, Striking from behind with hidden words.*

Across nearly all his textbooks, Abdulla Avloni consistently emphasized the development of friendship and solidarity among students. Examples include the stories “*The Alliance*” in “*The First Teacher*,” “*False Friend*” and “*The Bear’s Friendship*” in “*The Second Teacher*,” as well as “*Goodness Does Not Remain in the Ground*,” “*The Lion and the Bear*,” “*The Rooster and the Wolf*,” “*Ahmed and His Father*,” and “*The Blind and the Lame*.” Through these works, Avloni addressed the moral value of friendship and companionship as essential components of ethical education.

The method of cultivating honesty: One of the characteristic traditions of the Uzbek mentality is the special attention given to cultivating honesty in the younger generation. In the pedagogical and creative legacy of Abdulla Avloni, poems and stories promoting truthful speech and righteous behavior occupy an important place. A clear example of this is the poem “*The Lying Shepherd*,” written specifically for children. Abdulla Avloni defines truthfulness and correct speech as follows: “*Haqqaniyat means correctness in actions and truthfulness in words. By following the path of truth, a person cultivates a garden of health and a flower garden of happiness. Truth is the mother of such noble qualities as compassion, righteousness, and justice, which form the foundation of humanity.*” According to Avloni, truthfulness is manifested in two forms: truthfulness in actions and truthfulness in words. A person guided by intellect and conscience always speaks what he knows and sees, that is, the truth and what is right [10].

Honesty in action implies not betraying another person’s dignity or property, while honesty in speech means always telling the truth. An intelligent and conscientious individual consistently follows these principles. Avloni emphasizes that the opposite of honesty is lying, which he defines using the term *kizb* and describes liars as morally weak individuals [10]. He considered it one of the most sacred human duties to raise children in a way that prevents lying from becoming a habit and to protect their speech from moral vices. Avloni’s poems vividly illustrate the destructive consequences of dishonesty, warning that false reputation and deceit lead to lasting moral damage. His works demonstrate strong artistic and pedagogical influence drawn from folk traditions. Under the influence of folklore, Avloni composed several didactic poems, among which “*The Lying Shepherd*” can be effectively used in primary education to instill honesty through storytelling and moral reflection.

The method of cultivating patience and contentment: Patience and contentment occupy a central place in Abdulla Avloni’s pedagogical legacy. Numerous poems and stories devoted to these virtues are found in his works, particularly the chapter “*Patience*” in “*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*,” as well as stories such as “*Taqsim*,” “*Greed*,” and “*The Lion and the Bear*” from “*The First Teacher*.” Avloni defines patience as “*the ability to endure the hardships and misfortunes that befall a person*,” emphasizing that calmness and perseverance are essential in every endeavor [10]. According to him, patience enables individuals to achieve their goals thoughtfully and peacefully, while haste often leads to failure. Through these ideas, Avloni highlights patience and contentment as fundamental moral qualities necessary for personal growth and social harmony.

Everyone should act with patience and calmness in every undertaking. If a person works with patience, perseverance, and contentment, he will achieve his goal peacefully and steadily and gain satisfaction from his efforts. On the contrary, haste makes it difficult to reach one's goal. In the chapter "*Patience*," Abdulla Avloni advances morally significant ideas of self-control and contentment.

Abdulla Avloni's poems calling for knowledge and enlightenment, as well as the chapters "*Aqsami ilm*," "*Fatonat*," "*Hifzi lisan*," "*Ignorance*," and "*Haqqaniyyat*," address these issues in detail. According to Avloni, knowledge means the ability to read and write well and to master all the essential skills and sciences necessary for life. He believed that the future and progress of a nation depend on the level of knowledge, enlightenment, craftsmanship, and cultural development attained by its youth. Poems promoting knowledge and enlightenment occupy an important place in Avloni's pedagogical and scholarly heritage.

It should be noted that most of the poems included in the collection "*Literature or National Poems*" can be effectively used for the spiritual and moral education of students. Abdulla Avloni authored numerous poems and stories devoted to science and enlightenment that are valuable for students' moral development. Particularly noteworthy are works such as "*School*," "*A View from Our Environment*," "*My Dreams of the Future*," "*Promoting the School*," "*Happiness Exists*," and "*Ignorance*," as well as texts from "*The Second Teacher*," including "*School*," "*Kindergarten*," "*Call to School*," "*The Scourge of Ignorance*," "*Schoolboy*," "*From the Language of a Lazy Student*," and "*Lazy*."

The educational effectiveness of these works is explained by several factors: they are written in clear and simple language appropriate to students' age and level of understanding; they emphasize the importance of literacy, education, and intellectual development of the younger generation; they reflect national customs, traditions, and values in discussions of knowledge and enlightenment; they widely employ Islamic intellectual heritage that encourages learning; they are based on Uzbek folk pedagogy; they are influenced by the rich pedagogical and philosophical traditions of Eastern wisdom. Avloni emphasized the value of knowledge in the following words: "*Knowledge is a very high and sacred quality for a person. It reflects our actions and condition like a mirror and sharpens the mind like a sword. It distinguishes good from evil, right from wrong, and purity from impurity. Knowledge saves us from the darkness of ignorance, leads us to the world of culture, humanity, and enlightenment, and guides us away from immoral deeds*" [4].

Abdulla Avloni also wrote many poems and stories encouraging respect for parents. Notable examples include "*The Time of Education*" and "*Obedience*" from "*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*," as well as "*Family Debate*," "*Workers' Song*," "*A Mother's Words to Her Son*," "*A Son's Words to His Mother*," and "*Words to One's Wife*" from "*Literature or National Poems*." In "*The Second Teacher*," stories such as "*The Wise Gardener*," "*Ahmad and His Father*," and "*Soqi and His Mother*" further emphasize this theme. In the chapter "*Obedience*" of "*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*," Avloni defines obedience as one of the highest human virtues, stating that respect for parents, teachers, and elders is a fundamental moral quality [10]. The poem "*Family Debate*" portrays a conflict between an educated, forward-looking father and an ignorant mother who resists education, highlighting the importance of knowledge.

Similarly, "*Workers' Song*" conveys meaningful ideas about honoring parents. Generosity is another deeply rooted value in Uzbek culture. Abdulla Avloni devoted several poems and stories to this virtue, including the story "*Generosity*" from "*The Second Teacher*." In "*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*," he describes generosity as a noble human quality and contrasts it with greed, which

he considers morally destructive [10]. Through vivid examples, Avloni demonstrates that generosity brings social harmony, while miserliness leads to spiritual poverty. In conclusion, the spiritual and moral education of students through the scientific, pedagogical, and artistic heritage of Abdulla Avloni represents one of the most effective approaches within the modern educational system.

According to historical sources, Abdulla Avloni played a significant role not only in the development of education and culture of the Uzbek people, but also in the social and political life of neighboring Afghanistan. For a certain period, he served as the Minister of Public Education of Afghanistan and later worked as the Consul of the Soviet Union in Afghanistan [12]. This demonstrates that Avloni was not only a patriot and national figure, but also a prominent enlightener who actively promoted universal human values beyond national boundaries. Avloni viewed education as the main means of achieving future freedom and national liberation. He firmly believed that by educating the younger generation, it was possible to raise independent thinkers who would take responsibility for the fate of their country and society. He envisioned his students as individuals with their own civic position, capable of contributing to the progress of the nation. The realization of these ideals can be clearly observed today in the image of New Uzbekistan, which is undergoing profound renewal and transformation in the years of independence. Just as Jadid schools once represented a “new method” in education, contemporary reforms continue this innovative path based on new approaches to national development.

On August 3, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, held a meeting with representatives of the country’s creative intelligentsia, during which key issues in the fields of culture and art were discussed. The meeting emphasized the need for large-scale reforms in culture, mass media, literature, and art, as well as the importance of supporting young talents and introducing new ideas and initiatives. At the meeting, the President stated: *“There is another extremely important issue that never leaves our agenda, and it is directly related to the upbringing of our young generation, our children. As our great ancestor Abdulla Avloni said, this matter is truly a question of life or death for us, of salvation or destruction, of happiness or disaster”* [2]. In this context, Abdulla Avloni’s views on education are closely connected with the mentality, way of life, and national values of the Uzbek people. His pedagogical heritage serves as a foundation for a national model of education and remains a valuable source for educating spiritually mature, socially responsible, and intellectually developed young people.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it can be stated that Abdulla Avloni’s pedagogical activity played a crucial role in the fundamental renewal of public education at the beginning of the twentieth century. His work on creating textbooks, teaching manuals, and methodological resources laid a strong foundation for modern national education prior to the October Revolution. Avloni regarded education as the main means of social progress and national development.

In August 1917, Abdulla Avloni participated in the Second All-Russian Congress of Muslim Teachers held in Kazan. In the same year, together with Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhan, he took part in the establishment of the *“Teachers’ Society”* in Tashkent. The main purpose of this organization was to send talented young people to advanced foreign higher education institutions and to prepare progressive, nationally conscious specialists for higher educational institutions that were planned to be established in Turkestan. These initiatives reflect Avloni’s strategic vision of forming a modern, educated national elite. Although Avloni initially placed certain hopes on the reforms of the Tsarist government, its inconsistent and restrictive policies soon became evident.

Nevertheless, he did not abandon his educational mission and continued his pedagogical and enlightenment activities throughout the 1920s.

From 1930, he worked as a professor and head of the Uzbek language and literature department at the Faculty of Pedagogy of the Central Asian State University (now the National University of Uzbekistan), contributing significantly to higher education and teacher training. Avloni's school textbooks are of particular importance in the development of students' speech, expressive reading, and artistic thinking through dialogic and conversational teaching methods. For the first time, he included works by prominent writers such as M. Gorky, V. Mayakovsky, G'ulom, H. Olimjon, Oybek, K. Yashin, and Uyg'un in school curricula, providing students with systematic knowledge of their lives and creative activities. This approach demonstrates Avloni's understanding of literature as a powerful tool for moral, intellectual, and aesthetic education.

Conclusion

Throughout his life, Abdulla Avloni devoted his conscious activity to public education and enlightenment. His pedagogical views, grounded in national values and universal human ideals, remain relevant today. The study of Avloni's educational heritage offers significant pedagogical potential for teaching Jadid scientific heritage and for preparing future history teachers who are intellectually independent, morally mature, and socially responsible. Suggestions: To actively incorporate Abdulla Avloni's pedagogical ideas and texts into the curricula of higher education institutions that train future history teachers. To use Avloni's works as a source for developing students' moral education, critical thinking, and national consciousness. To apply Avloni's dialogic and literary-based teaching methods in modern history and social science education. To conduct further interdisciplinary research on Avloni's pedagogical heritage in the context of contemporary educational reforms.

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